

MOTIVATING THE FOREIGN AND THE SECOND LANGUAGE LEARNERS FOR ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT

Mohammad Taher Hossain Salim

Lecturer

Mohammad Humayun Kabir

Associate Professor

Department of English Language and Literature

International Islamic University Chittagong

154/A, College Road, Chawak Bazar, Chittagong- 4203

Bangladesh

Email: [1taher.iiuc@gmail.com](mailto:taher.iiuc@gmail.com), [2Humayun002003@yahoo.com](mailto:Humayun002003@yahoo.com)

Abstract

The paper discusses the concept of motivation and the motivational impact upon the language achievement of the foreign language (FL) and second language (L2) learners. It also deals with the critical studies of the existing theories of motivation and their pedagogical and functional aspect in the FL/L2 teaching/learning arena. The study, thus, shows that teachers and teaching/learning materials have significant roles to play in motivating the demotivated learners and, therefore, suggests the expected motivational activities in the language classroom.

Key words: Motivation - Integrative Motivation - Instrumental Motivation - Machiavellian Motivation - Motivational Activities

Introduction

The term motivation is often used by the applied linguists, teachers and learners alike when they try to ascertain the reason of success or failure in Foreign Language (FL) acquisition. Motivation is considered as one of the key factors that determines proportional success of the FL/L2 learning. This psychological aspect provides the primary impetus to initiate learning the FL/L2 and it also works as the driving force to sustain the long and often tedious learning process. We presume, without sufficient motivation, even individuals with extraordinary aptitude cannot succeed in target language learning.

From our experience (as learners and teachers), we have noticed that this fundamental concept of motivation does not get due attention and concentration from our language teachers and education administrators. They still believe punishment to be the only remedy or cure for those who fail to achieve the FL/L2. We further observe that the teaching/learning materials and the classrooms in our context have still remained highly demotivating. The paper, therefore, aims at focusing on the key issues and existing challenges in the motivation in hope to facilitate FL/L2 teaching and learning in Bangladesh.

Motivation

It refers to the factors or the reasons that stimulate the interest of somebody to do something. It is usually defined as 'a psychological trait' which leads people to achieve some goal. It 'refers to the directed effort individual learners make to learn the language,' (Ellis, 1994, p.509). Motivation, a non-language influence, can make an individual more successful in learning a second language than other individuals. Motivated individuals are believed to learn foreign/second language faster and to a greater degree. Shekan (1989) states, 'In general, motivation appears to be the second strongest predictor of success, trailing only aptitude' (as cited in Gass and Selinker, 2001, p. 349). Language learners are found more enthusiastic and zealous if they are motivated. 'Language learning theory has generally accepted the axiom that language learners with higher levels of motivation will be higher achievers' (Chen, Warden and Chang, 2005, p. 610). It is agreed that motivation 'provides the primary impetus to initiate learning the L2 and later the driving force to sustain the long and often tedious learning process; indeed, all other factors involved in L2 acquisition presuppose motivation to some extent' (Dornyei, 1998, p.117).

Motivation is an example of a psychological factor which is 'clearly variable'. A learner's motivation may change from time to time and undoubtedly it is influenced by some external features. Language teachers acknowledge that motivation is a vital factor in learning second language. 'SLA research also views motivation as key factor in L2 learning' (Ellis, 1994, p. 508). Though in research as Ellis (1994) maintains, 'there is widespread recognition that motivation is of great importance for successful L2 acquisition ,but there is less agreement about what motivation actually consists of'(p.36). It is a very difficult construct which has very loose boundaries. It is not something that can easily be measured in the same way that, even if imperfectly,

language aptitude or proficiency can. That is why Covington (1998) rightly said, 'Motivation, like the concept of gravity, is easier to describe (in terms of its outward , observable effects) than it is to define. Of course, this has not stopped people from trying it'(p.1). We will discuss and examine different kinds of motivation and their impact on Second Language Acquisition in the light of the findings of different studies below.

Intrinsic and Extrinsic Motivation

Motivation may be divided into two types – intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. Intrinsic motivation derives from the 'personal interests and inner needs' of a learner. According to Jhonson and Jhonson (Eds) (1998), 'A sense of achievement, self-esteem, pride in solving the problem, engagement of the class...etc.' (p. 220), are found in a learner who is intrinsically motivated. It is as if 'being within the task itself'. Dornyei (2001, p. 53) maintains, 'the intrinsic value of L2 learning is associated with the learners' interest in and anticipated enjoyment of the language learning activity'. We understand intrinsic motivation concerns behaviour performed for its own sake in order to experience enjoyment and pleasure such as the joy of doing a particular activity or satisfying one's inquisitiveness. Students who lack intrinsic motivation often desire variety, excitement and novelty. Effective teachers should choose different teaching methods and learning materials that will motivate their students. Teachers can use popular culture like commercial movies, highly stimulating music, etc. in classroom teaching. If it is a young learners' classroom, teachers may consider introducing some widely popular cartoons such as Tom and Jerry, Doremon etc. which the learners enjoy most. Teachers should design teaching materials in such a way that will fulfil the students' psychological and social needs and evoke their effective emotion and imagination.

On the other hand, extrinsic motivation derives from the external sources 'such as material rewards'. Hence it is therefore, external to the task. 'Prizes for doing well, getting the job of one's choice, a higher position, gaining some certificates on a test score,' etc. Jhonson and Jhonson (Eds)(1998, p. 220), will work as extrinsic motivation in a language learner. It involves performing behaviour as a means to an end, that is, to receive some extrinsic reward such as achieving good grades or avoiding punishment. In Bangladesh, we find that extrinsic motivation is more dominant among school going students than the intrinsic motivation. Most of the students read books, memorize answers / prepared notes of the probable questions or go to coaching centres or keep house tutor to prepare notes for them in order to achieve better grades. A good number of students learn English lesson in order to avoid punishment.

It is really difficult to say whether extrinsic or intrinsic motivation is more powerful. In fact, this query leads to consideration of 'learner's scale of values'. It is the learners who can say which motivation works within them in learning L2. It may be found that a sense of achievement i.e. intrinsic motivation is working in some learners. However, we can see a completely different attitude in other group of learners who emphasize extrinsic benefits of success and it keeps them working on the goal of mastery.

Integrative motivation

It makes a learner desirous to learn a language in order to communicate with people of another culture who use it as their medium of communication. It involves an interest in learning an L2 because of 'a sincere and personal interest in the people and culture represented by the other language group' (Lambert, 1974, p. 98). The research works by some scholars show that there is a strong and consistent correlation between integrative motivation and L2 learning. Glikzman initiated

series of studies (Glikzman 1976, Glikzman, Gardner and Smythe, 1982) found that integrative motivation has a significant role in making learner active which helps a learner to acquire L2 easily by exerting more effort. Observing Glikzman's studies, Ellis (1994, 512) states, 'the higher their integrative motivation, the more these classroom behaviours are evident'. After the careful observation of the research done by Gardner and Lambert (1972) and Shaaban and Ghaith (2000), Chen, Warden and Cheng (2005) remark that 'language learning motivation research results have tended to support the paramount importance of integrative motivation. It is found that 'learners with integrative motivation are more active in class and less likely to drop out.'

Integrative motivation is fruitful because language skills are perceived as essential to participation in the social groups that use the target language. 'Noels, Pelletier, Clement and Vallerand (2000) recognize the pre-eminent importance previously granted to the integrative motivation orientation but specify that this may be the case only in specific socio-cultural contexts' (cited in Chen et al, 2005, p. 612). A person with integrative motivation has to be liberal and willing to acculturated with the target language group and he needs a positive temperament towards everything the L2 is related with. Hence Dornyei(2001, p. 54) argues 'languages are socially and culturally bound, their effective study requires a positive disposition towards everything the L2 is associated with: its culture, its speakers, its influence'. Cook (1991, p. 73) also holds, 'the more that a student admires the target culture – reads its literature, visits it on holiday, looks for opportunities of practising the language, and so on – the more successful the student will be in the L2 classroom'.

Despite the research works which have revealed that integrative motivation is a vital factor in learning L2, some studies, however,

have failed to find a positive relationship between integrative motivation and L2 learning. Oller, Baca, and Vigil (1977, p. 173) find 'that Mexican women in California who rated Anglo people negatively were more successful in learning English than those who rated them positively'. Oller and Perkins (1978, p. 85) suggest that people may be motivated 'to excel because of negative attitudes towards the target language community'. They refer to it as '**Machiavellian Motivation**'. A negative feeling may lead to a desire to manipulate and overcome the people of the target language. Central Intelligence Agency (CIA) and Federal Bureau of Investigation (FBI) and many other secret intelligence agents of the world are learning Arabic in order to tackle the Al -Qaeda activities as the Al-Qaeda members usually communicate in Arabic most of the time. We find another instance of Machiavellian motivation in the staff of East India Company who established a British colony in the Indian sub-continent. Most of the top ranking East India Company officials could speak Bangla and they acquired this language competence purely to manipulate and overcome the people of greater India.

Instrumental Motivation

Learners with instrumental motivation want to learn a language because it will be useful for certain 'instrumental' goals, such as getting a job, passing an exam etc. It is more concerned with the practical value and utilities of learning L2. Here external incentives and influences work as determinants of learners' motivational strength. A learner with this motivation learns a language for an external motive unrelated to its use by native speakers – earning extra money, getting a promotion, pursuing further studies, pursuing hobbies and other leisure activities where the L2 is a requirement. According to Larsen-Freeman and Long (1991, p. 173) this type of motivation motivates a learner 'to learn an L2 for utilitarian purposes, such as furthering a career, improving social

status or meeting an educational requirement'. The findings indicate that instrumental motivation can play a vital role in learning a foreign language. 'Instrumental motivation can effectively motivate language learners, especially when they value the return on investment' Chen et al. (2005). Ellis (1994, p. 512) cites that Naiman, Frohlich, Stern, and Todesco (1978) have found a relationship between instrumental motivation and classroom behaviours of the students. 'They (students) were also able to show that a number of classroom behaviours associated with effort (such as hand raising) were significantly related to L2 achievement'. Gardner and MacIntyre (1991) launched a research where learners respond to statements such as 'studying French can be important because it is useful for one's career.' They equate '**instrumental motivation**' with giving students a financial reward for performing a task successfully. Their studies investigated the influence of an instrumental motivation on learning. It is found that it depends on situational / cultural context of learning. 'Thus, whereas instrumental motivation has been found to be only a weak predictor of foreign language achievement in several Canadian studies (Gardner and Lambert, 1972), it appears to be much more powerful in other context where learners have little or no interest in target-language culture and few or no opportunities to interact with its members.' (Ellis 1994,p. 514). Dunkel (1948,cited in Gardner and MacIntyre, 1992) offered financial incentives to students learning Farsi and found the students very much enthusiastic to do better. Gardner and MacIntyre (1991) also carried out a study like Dunkel. They asked 46 university psychology students to participate in pair- associated (English-French) vocabulary task and offered \$10 if they succeeded. They also asked same number of students just to do their best. In that study it was found that students who were offered financial reward did significantly better than those who were not offered. But from their

more observations they found that students apply extra effort as long as there is reward. This led 'Gardner and MacIntyre to claim that once any chance for receiving a reward is eliminated, learners may cease applying extra effort' (Ellis, 1994, p. 514).

In Bangladesh we notice that most of our students do not learn English (L2) to integrate into English culture, rather they learn L2 (English) in order to get a suitable job at home or abroad because proficiency in English is considered as an extra and most desired qualification. So it is instrumental motivation, not integrative, that inspires our students to learn English. We have also observed that our students try heart and soul to learn English when they take preparation for Bangladesh Civil Service (BCS) examination in Bangladesh as BCS cadre jobs are very worthwhile in our country. One of the present researchers has the personal experience that it is instrumental motivation which inspired him to study for an MA degree in English Language Teaching (ELT) at the University of Essex, England in order to make his position demanding and rewarding in his department and university.

Integrative or Instrumental Motivation

In the above discussion, we have seen that both integrative and instrumental motivation can play a vital role in learning L2. Like Gardner, it appears to us that instrumental motivation emerges as significant factor only in some studies, whereas integrative motivation has been proved as an important factor in L2 achievement. It is interesting to note that learners, of course, have both integrative and instrumental motivation. Muchnick and Wolfe (1982) undertook a study among 337 students of Spanish in high schools in the United States and found both types of motivation active in them. Ely (1986 b) found similar result in his study which involved first year university students of Spanish in the US.

From our experience, we have noticed that language (English) learners in Bangladesh have both types of motivation when they learn L2. Our learners learn English to pass exam, to obtain an impressive grade, to get scholarship, to discover the rich world of knowledge, to run office activities, to communicate with foreigners, to get a lucrative job abroad, to migrate to a developed country like USA, UK, Australia, Canada, etc. So it is rather impossible to distinguish whether instrumental or integrative motivation is functioning in them in their pursuit of learning English. Sometimes both types of the motivation work together. However, we find a good number of students in Bangladesh who have neither integrative nor instrumental motivation especially at school level.

From our observation it is found that neither of the above mentioned types inspires them when they learn English. As a result L2 learning as well as teaching becomes a very complicated task for the learners and teachers alike. Cook (1991, p. 73) also finds it as an inevitable reality when he writes 'nevertheless students will find it difficult to learn a second language in the classroom if they have neither instrumental nor integrative motivation, as is probably often the case in school language teaching'. It is true that school children are too immature to realise the necessity of learning L2. Majority of them do not have any contact with the foreign culture and nor they have any particular interest in it. Above all, they are too immature to realize the value of leaning English.

Motivation in the classroom and in materials

We are to accept that teachers' motivation in the classroom can remarkably encourage a learner in achieving an L2. It will boost a student's confidence as well as help him to realize the importance of leaning. In relation to language teaching and learning, 'there has been a consistent move towards motivation-

enhancing learning activities'. In their research 'Crookes and Schmidt (1989) describe many ways in which teachers try to influence their students' motivation, particularly appealing to effects intrinsic to the classroom situation ...' (Jhonson and Jhonson, Eds.1999, p. 224). It is also proved that materials, too, can motivate the students in learning an L2. If the learners find the materials authentic, personalised, localised, learner-centred, etc., it will be motivating to them. Stevick (1971) mentions five types of reward that could be built into materials and would encourage students to persevere and succeed. They are i) Relevance ii) Completeness iii) Authenticity iv) Satisfaction and v) Immediacy.

i. Relevance: Teaching materials and their contents should be relevant to the students' own language needs. A lesson might be full of lofty ideals of science/philosophy/literature. May be it has a great value for the scholars. Indeed, it will have no impact on learners if it does not reflect learners' need.

ii. Completeness: It refers to the inclusion of all the language elements necessary for the stated aims of the course. We claim that our secondary (Grade IX-X) and higher secondary (Grade XI-XII) English course books are designed on the basis of Communicative Language Teaching. But two important skills e.g. speaking and listening have been ignored in the books, which has made the books incomplete.

iii. Authenticity: Both linguistic and cultural authenticity should be taken with great importance when the teaching materials are designed. It is evident that our students at primary, secondary and higher secondary levels never get the opportunity of using authentic materials.

iv. Satisfaction: Learners' satisfaction is one of the key factors in achieving L2. The students should complete each lesson with the

feeling that he has benefited more than simply progressed. It will highly motivate them and will make them enthusiastic and encourage them to come to the subsequent lessons. As our language classrooms are teacher-centred and as learner autonomy is still unknown in our teaching culture, we can hardly ensure learners' satisfaction.

v. Immediacy: The teaching materials should be designed in such a way that the students should be able to use the materials straight away. The big problem that we notice in our course materials is the gap between theory and practice. We assume that our textbooks are designed and taught ignoring the value of immediacy in them.

Can de-motivation detract from effective learning?

It is true that motivation encourages a learner to learn L2. It is also shown that success in learning may motivate a learner further to learn L2. The relationship between motivation and achievement is an interactive one. 'A high level of motivation does stimulate learning but perceived success in achieving L2 goals can help to maintain existing motivation and even create new types. Conversely, a vicious circle of low motivation=low achievement=lower motivation can develop' (Ellis, 1994, p. 515). Teachers often give the impression to the students that English literature is a very tough subject. We have noticed that in the University of Chittagong, Bangladesh, most teachers repeatedly remind the students that it is not easy to get a second class from the English department. In the very opening lectures, the students are informed of the horrible results of the students of previous years. Most of the students are scared and subsequently it affects their academic career. So, we believe that demotivation can detract from effective learning.

Overcoming demotivation

Demotivation may occur due to many reasons like teaching materials, teaching environment, teaching method, testing method, etc. It is important that learners should overcome it. Demotivated learners can be helped back onto the motivation train by being taught how to use strategies more effectively. It is believed that it will lead to a greater success in learning than before. For example, Oxford and Nyikos (1989 as cited in Macaro, 2003) found that motivation was the highest predictor of high strategy use among university under-graduate. From various studies it is perceived that the correlation between strategy use, motivation and achievement in language learning is a strong one. Dornyei (2001, p. 31) mentions following three motivational conditions which will be very effective means of overcoming demotivation:

- i. Appropriate teacher behaviours and a good relationship with the students.
- ii. A pleasant and supportive atmosphere.
- iii. A cohesive learner group with appropriate group norms.

What teachers think about motivation

Research has shown that teachers can play a crucial role to motivate learners. Present researchers will present a list of guidelines based on the views of practising teachers and teacher – researchers as to what aids motivation.

Dornyei and Csizer (1998) surveyed 200 practising teachers and suggest the following ‘**ten commandments**’ for motivating language learners:

1. Set a personal example with your own behaviour.
2. Create a pleasant relaxed atmosphere in the classroom.

3. Present the tasks properly.
4. Develop a good relationship with the learners.
5. Increase the learners’ linguistic self-confidence.
6. Make the language classes interesting.
7. Promote learner autonomy.
8. Personalise the learning process.
9. Increase the learners’ goal-orientedness.
10. Familiarise the learners with the target language culture.

Williams and Burden (1997), on the other hand, provide some guidelines. Here the present researchers state some of them.

1. Discuss with learners why they are carrying out activities.
2. Involve learners in making decisions related to learning the language.
3. Recognise people as individuals.
4. Build up individuals’ beliefs in themselves.
5. Build up a supportive learning environment.
6. Give feedback that is informational.

Teachers in the Chambers (1993) survey suggested the following as a way of motivating reluctant learners.

1. Provide immediate rewards such as ‘well done stickers’.
2. Improve the teacher-pupil relationship by giving them time and support.
3. Negotiate an agreement on what is acceptable and expected.
4. Insist on small groups where behaviour is more easily managed.
5. Materials and tasks should be appropriate to pupils’ interests and level of ability.
6. Offer a variety of tasks and materials.

From various research findings we can perceive that teachers can play key role to motivate language learners. They hold a strong authority by which they can even assist the demotivated students.

Conclusion: We know that motivation is goal-directed. However, 'it is also partly dependent on information about success or failure'. So many learners need '*immediate feedback on how well they are performing or how they compare with others...*' (Johnson and Johnson, (eds.), 1998, p. 220). If learners notice that their progress is satisfactory, they are doing better in comparison with others, their success will strengthen their motivation to complete the rest of the work. So it appears that there is a close relation between motivation and achievement. A positively motivated person can achieve a language more easily while a demotivated person may consider it impossible

as learning a language is a time consuming effort. Sometimes it requires months and years, which may lead to frustration. It is motivation which makes a person more **persistent** and gives him **tolerance of frustration**. It will also help the learner to cope with anxiety that occurs during learning process.

The whole discussion above reveals that motivation contributes to effective learning of L2. But the relationship is complex, the evidence is sometimes incomplete. Motivation has been found to be 'strongly related to Foreign Language (FL) achievement'.

References:

1. Brophy, J.E. (1998): Motivating Students to Learn. McGraw-Hill, Boston, MA.
2. Chambers, G. (1993): 'Taking the 'de' out of demotivation'. *Language Learning Journal*, 7, 13-16
3. Chen, F.J., Warden, C.A., and Chang, H. (2005): 'Motivators That Do Not Motivate: The Case of Chinese EFL Learners and the Influence of Culture on Motivation'. *TESOL Quarterly*, Vol-39, Nov1.
4. Cook, V. (1991): Second Language Learning and Language Teaching. London. Edward Arnold.
5. Crookes, G. and Schmidt, R. (1989): Motivation : reopening the research agenda. University of Hawaii, **Working Papers in ESL**, 8.
6. Conington, M.V. (1998): The Will to Learn: A Guide for Motivating Young People. Cambridge. Cambridge University Press.
7. Dornyei, Z. and Csizer, K. (1998): 'Ten commandments for motivating language learners : results of an empirical study'. **Language Teaching Research**, 2 (203-29)
8. Dornyei, Z. (2001): Motivational Strategies in the Language Classroom. Cambridge University Press.
9. Ellis, R. (1989a): 'Classroom learning styles and their effect on second language acquisition: a study of two learners'. **System** 17:257.
10. Ellis, R. (1994): The Study of Second Language Acquisition. Oxford University Press.
11. Ely, C. (1986b). 'Language learning motivation : a descriptive and casual analysis'. *Modern Language Journal* 70:28-35
12. Gass, S. & Selinker, L. (2nd ed.) (2001): Second Language Acquisition ,An Introductory Course. Lawrence Erlbaum Associates, Inc., Publishers. Mahwah.
13. Johnson, K. and Johnson, H. (eds.) (1998): Encyclopaedic Dictionary of Applied Linguistics. Blackwell Publishers Ltd.
14. Lambert, W. (1974): 'Culture and language as factors in learning and education' in F. Aboud and Meade (eds.) 1974.
15. Larsen-Freeman, D. , & Long, M. (1991): An Introduction to Second Language Acquisition Research. London. Longman.

16. Macaro,E. (2003): Teaching and Learning a Second Language. A Guide to Recent Research and its Applications.Continuum.London.
17. MacIntyre,P. and R.Gardner(1991a): *'Methods and results in the study of foreign language anxiety: a review of the literature'*. **Language Learning 41**.
18. MacIntyre,P. and R.Gardner(1991b): Language anxiety: its relationship to other anxieties and to processing in native and second languages. **Language Learning 41**.
19. Muchnick,A. and D.Wolfe.(1982): *'Attitudes and motivations of American students of Spanish'*.**Canadian Modern Language Review 38**.
20. Naiman, N., M.Frohlich, H. Stern, and A. Todesco. 1978. *The Good Language Learner. Research in Education Series No 7*.Toronto: The Ontario Institute for Studies in Education
21. Oller,J.,L.Baca,and A.Vigil.(1977): *'Attitudes and attained proficiency in ESL: a sociolinguistic study of Mexican Americans in the Southwest'*. **TESOL Quarterly11**:173-83
22. Oller,J. and K,Perkins (1978): *'Intelligence and language proficiency as sources of variance in self- reported affective variables'*. **Language Learning 28: 85-97**
23. Oxford,R.,& Nyikos,M.(1989): Variable affecting choice of language learning strategies by university students. **Modern Language Journal73,3(291-300)**.
24. Skehan,P.(1989): Individual Differences in Second Language Learning. London:Edward Arnold.
25. Stevick,E.(1971): Evaluating and adapting language materials. In H.Allen and R.Capbell(eds). Teaching English as Second Language.2nd edn.New York :McGraw-Hill.
26. Williams,M., &Burden,R.(1997): Psychology for Language Teachers. Cambridge. Cambridge University Press.

